

A Sociological Account on Online Community and Its Peculiarities

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Abstract

An online community refers to a group of people who interact and engage with each other primarily through the Internet. These communities can take various forms, such as forums, social media groups, chat rooms, and specialized platforms. People join online communities to connect with others who share similar interests, hobbies, goals, or demographics. Online communities provide a platform for individuals to discuss, share, and exchange information on various topics. They can be centered around a specific subject, such as a particular hobby, professional field, or fandom, or they can be more general, aiming to foster social connections and provide support. The following article presents the ongoing patterns and changes in online communities.

Keywords: Network Society, Online Community, Social Networking, Social Computing

Introduction

The global presence of cyber community and its impact on social life can hardly be denied because it is a social reality, though “cyber-community”, the very concept itself poses a long-term debate related to the issue of whether it can at all be called a community. The Communication scholar Steven G. Jones, who coined the term “Cybersociety” in the year 1995, had endeavored much to produce enough academic evidence to establish these new “social formations in cyberspace” as “Cyber communities” which he believed to have certain similarities with the community in reality. Jones’s view was augmented by Socio-internet scholar Douglas Schuler (NewCommunity Networks, 1997) who felt the need for the establishment of “a new community – one that is fundamentally devoted to democratic problem solving – needs to be fashioned from the remnants of the old”, and he emphasizes on the role of computer networking strengthening organizations, providing local information, and developing the bonds of civic life and conviviality that lead to social capital. Thus, according to him the new form of interconnected community with hardware and software resources surpasses the limit of time and space and allows new forms of democratic discourse and participation.

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The debate regarding the very issue whether the term, community, can be applied in cyberspace have been persisting for long, until Matthew Williams takes *“the stance arguing despite the lack of physicality, communities can be formed and maintained in cyberspace”*. It, however, took considerably a long time (till early 90s) for socio-internet scholars such as Benedikt(1991), Rheingold (1991,1993), Reid (1991, 1995), Curtis(1992), MacKinnon(1992,1996), Hauben(1993) Heim (1993), Derry(1994), Jones (1995) and others to institute the claim of existence of cyber-communities; only after these researchers were able to establish *Cybersociety's* fundamental existence they might possibly begin to study in-depth the burgeoning communities of which Jones speaks.

In the preface of his latest edited book *“Social Computing: Concepts, Methodologies, Tools, and Applications”* (2010). Subhasis Dasgupta takes the definition of **Social Computing** from Wikipedia according to which it *“refers to an area of computer science that is the intersection of social behaviour and computational systems”* and he points out that social computing implies two components: a social behaviour component and computational / technical component. According to him the technical component builds the environment in which people interact. He adds another important definition of social computing which is *“Social Computing is the use of technology in networked communication systems by communities of the people for one or more goals.”* He also ensures that social computing may interchangeably be used with such other terms as *“online communities”*, *“Web 2.0, virtual communities”* and *“Social networking”* and these definitions sometimes overlap (Parameswaran and Whinston, 2007). He attempts to explain *online community* through two definitions:

1. *Online communities are defined as groups of people who meet and interact with others, are connected by a specific interest, are brought together by the means of a technical platform, and can establish social relationship or a sense of belonging to the group* (Leimeister et al 2008) “.
- 2.” *a virtual community refers to people with a common or shared purpose, whose interactions are governed by policies in the form of tacit assumptions, rituals, protocols, rules and laws and whose use of computer systems to support and mediate social interaction and to facilitate a sense of togetherness* (Preece2000),”

Thus, he tries to depict that the definitions of online communities, virtual communities, and Social Computing overlap. According to him, Social Computing takes many forms, such as RSS blogs, search engines, podcasts, wikis, and social bookmarking or tagging. Thus *“common citizens have flocked to social computing websites such as Facebook, MySpace, and Twitter in the millions, making these sites the fastest growing properties on the web.*

Abhijit Roy opines in his article *“Online Communities and Social Networking”* (2010) that technology empowers scholars to conceive of communities without physical or face-to-face contact especially with the advent of *“Information Super highway”* in the 50’s and 60’s. Ever since the development of www or the World Wide Web online communities which have increasingly appeared *“have limitless boundaries across every corner of the globe”*. Roy seeks to study several topologies of these phenomena, various motivations of the people to join such communities, how marketers create social

bonds that enhance social relationships, and their strategies to build online communities. He most interestingly adds in his article a host of definitions of online communities from various sources which is really appreciable. The major definitions are as follows:

- Social aggregations that emerge from the Net when enough people carry on public discussions long enough, with sufficient human feeling, to form webs of personal relationships in cyberspace (Rheingold,1993).
- Groups of people who communicate with each other via electronic media, rather than face-to-face. (Romm, Pliskin and Clarke 1997).
- Computer Mediated spaces where there is a potential for an integration of content and communication with an emphasis on member-generated content. (Hegel and Armstrong 1997)
- Online publics are symbolically delineated computer-mediated spaces, whose existence is relatively transparent and open, that allow groups of individuals to attend and contribute.

Typologies of Online Communities

According to Roy Online communities may take different shapes and sizes and their memberships may range from a handful few to millions. "These communities may extend from active forums like discussion groups and chat rooms to passive ones like e-mails and bulletin boards". Since these communities have no territorial restrictions as well as delimitations, their size may constitute much bigger than the communities in reality and many millions(if not billions or trillions) can thus reside in such communities of World Wide Web, e.g., Facebook now claims to have a population more than 900 active members. Internet scholars have proposed various classification schemes for the configurations of the online communities. Hegel and Armstrong (1997) propose four major types of online communities based on people's desire to meet basic human needs: interests, relationship, fantasy and transaction, Jones and Rafaeli (2000) further divide these communities by social structure, i.e., communities formed based on social networks, for example online voluntary associations, cyber inns and the like, and technology base, i.e., types of technology platforms, for example e-mail lists, Usenet groups and so on.

Kozinets (2002) proposed the four types of communities as dungeons, i.e., online environments where players interact, such as for online video games, circles, (interest structured collection of common interests), rooms (computer-mediated environments where people interact socially in real time), and boards (online communities organize around interest specific bulletin boards)

Finally, Macchiette and Roy (1992) proposed a typology of affinity communities that can also be used for classifying online communities. They defined communities as either being: professional (e.g., doctors lawyers, etc.), common interest, (e.g., hobbies, interests), Demographic (e.g., by gender, age, etc), cause-based(Sierra Club, Green Peace) and market generated(e.g.; Disney, Nitendo) communities. These communities may also be constructed in the online environment.

It is also interesting to make other dichotomous distinctions of online communities such as : (a) formal (e.g. associations) vs. Informal communities, (b) commercial(which offers goods and services to make revenues that in turn fuels community operation) vs. non- commercial(communities created from the ground up by a group of individuals, e.g., with an interest in stamp collection) open or public (where

everyone regardless of their qualification and individual profile can enter the community and participate)vs closed or private (where outsiders are not allowed into the community, or where membership is very difficult to obtain)

Motivations.

Roy sums up the motivational factors for members to join a community roughly in to four:

1. Affiliation, to get affiliated by the group or members of the community.
2. Information about experiences, ideas and issues.
3. Recreation through meeting people, playing around, sharing stories etc.
4. Transaction for those who join a website for buying and trading possessions.

Mode of Participation.

According to Roy participation may take place in various ways, for example, through e-mails, chat rooms, discussion groups, online events, blogs, social networking websites (e.g., MySpace, Facebook, Orkut, etc), sharing photographs (e.g. Flickr), wikis (Wikipedia),bulletin board, and son on.

Characteristics of Online Communities

Abhijit Roy finds certain characteristics are prevalent with the growth and maturity of online communities. He cites Adler and Christopher (1999) who identify six such characteristics:

1. Cohesion: Members seek a sense of belonging and develop group identity over time.
2. Relationships: Community members interact and develop friendships over time.
3. Effectiveness: the group has an impact on members' lives.
4. Help: Community members feel comfortable asking for and receiving help from each other.
5. Language: Members develop shared communication tools that have a unique meaning within the community.
6. Self-Regulation: The community develops a system for policing itself and set ground rules of operation.

Benefits to members

Adler and Christopher (1999) further point out that the members of the online community develop various emotional benefits depending on the communities that they join. They include inclusion, shared information and experiences, need fulfillment, and mutual influence among others.

Degree Of Connectedness in Online Communities

In accordance with Roy the degree of connectedness in online communities also plays a significant role in how an online community develops. They can be classified as weak, limited, or strong. This primarily depends on the degree of interactivity between and among members.

- Weak: Members of these sites have no opportunities of interacting with each other on a one-on-one basis, for example, newspaper Websites and Corporate Websites.
- Limited: these communities offer limited opportunities for members to interact with others, for example, reading and posting information or opinions.
- Strong: these communities offer chat rooms and message boards and allow users to form strong bonds with each other.

Internet scholars have shown that both strong and weak connections have their own advantages. While weak ties are shown to facilitate such tasks as finding jobs (Granovetter 1973) strong ties are required to facilitate major changes in the communities (Krackhardt 1992)".

Fig - 1 (Source: Abhijit Roy (2010), Online Communities and Social Networking; Social Computing: concept, Methodologies, Tools, and Application, Subhasish Dasgupta (ed), p-48, vol-1)

Stages of Online Community Life Cycle

Roy suggests that online community building is a multifaceted process that includes several steps or stages. He cites Kim's (2000) proposal for a five-stage online community-building process as follows:

1. Visitor: These are individuals who 'lurk' in the online community, yet do not participate in them.
2. Novices: They are new members or "newbies" who are usually passive and are busy learning the rules and culture of the online community and thus are not actively engaged in it.
3. Regulars: They have established members comfortably participating in the exchanges and making up the largest segment of the online community.
4. Leaders: These members are volunteers, contractors, and staff who create topics and plan activities that keep the online community running.
5. Elders: They are respected members of the online community who are always eager to share their knowledge and pass along the culture of the community to the newer members.

The scholars like Mohammed, Fisher, Jaworski, and Paddison (2004) who alternatively suggest four relationship stages: *awareness*, *exploration/expansion*, *commitment* and *dissolution*, and verifying the level of intensity patterns as online community members go through membership life cycles. At the initial "awareness" stage, members have the lowest intensity levels and are likely to be considered visitors up until the exploration stage. At this second stage, these novices develop greater intensity and commitment to the site. The equity-building efforts over time translate into the online members becoming regulars and subsequently leaders or elders. Finally, over time even the most committed members outgrow a community and become "departing friends." Farmer (1994) had earlier described four similar stages through which individuals in online communities mature. According to him, members begin as *passives* (attending a community, yet not actively engaging in it), and then go on to become *actives*

Fig - 2 (Source: Abhijit Roy 2010), Online Communities and Social Networking; Social Computing: concept, Methodologies, Tools and Application, Subhashish Dasgupta (ed), p-50, Vol -1)

Conclusion

When participating in online communities, it's important to maintain respectful and constructive interactions, adhere to community guidelines, and be mindful of privacy and security considerations. Overall, online communities provide a valuable platform for individuals to connect, learn, and engage with others who share their interests or goals. However, it's important to note that the network society is not without its challenges. Issues such as the digital divide (unequal access to technology), privacy concerns, online misinformation, and social fragmentation are some of the complex issues that arise in the context of network society. Overall, the network society describes the social, economic, and cultural transformations brought about by ICTs, highlighting the pervasive influence of networked communication and the reconfiguration of social structures and dynamics in contemporary societies.

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